

Double Resonances and Quantized Oscillatory Particles?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 4, 2019

Some quantum mechanical scenarios may be mathematically simplified by making use of a simpler quantum problem. For example, the problem of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the wall can be solved and the wavefunctions used as a basis for a new problem created by adding a finite potential to the interior. For the harmonic oscillator, one may write the general wavefunction as a product of the ground state wavefunction and another function (which is found to be a Hermite polynomial). If a Hamiltonian may be written in terms of a simpler Hamiltonian with known solutions plus a small perturbation term, the new wavefunction may be described as a mixed state (in terms of the simpler Hamiltonian). Finally, even traditional quantum statistical mechanics makes use of single particle resonance states and the photons which allow one to jump from one to another, although one does not create a mixed state in such a case.

Given that one solves a simpler quantum problem first, quantized wavefunction solutions appear with specific energy gaps. In the new, more complicated problem, the simpler wavefunctions serve as a basis and “on the surface” it appears there is already quantization in the problem based on the energy level gaps of the simpler states. These may perhaps be thought of in terms of oscillatory quantized particles, say phonons or other particles. Thus, the new problem contains a potential or perturbative potential which may operate together with these oscillatory particles, or the oscillatory particles operate directly with the wavefunction as in the case of the oscillator. In such cases, it is as if one has a double resonance. The “simpler” problem creates quantized gaps and possibly oscillatory particles which are then used in the more complicated problem. A question arises as to whether this double resonance is a mathematical convenience or represents physical phenomena in the sense of the first resonance physically existing and restricting quantization of the second. In this note, we try to investigate these ideas.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Walls

In (1), the authors describe the spatial wavefunction of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls as $C_1 \sin(kx-b)$. They specifically call $k^2/2m$, where $k=6.28n/L$, the average energy and so k is a kind of root mean square result. The authors list the Fourier transform weights as:

$$f_p = C_2 \sin(L/2p - n \cdot 3.14/2) / (p^2/2m - E_n) \text{ where } E_n = (\hbar k_n)^2/2m \quad ((1))$$

(Here the center of the box is at $x=0$.)

The idea seems to be that all possible p values are allowed and it is only overall interference which leads to $\sin(kx-b)$ which vanishes at the endpoints. Thus, a resonance seems to be established with the walls of the box. An interesting point, however, is that:

$$\sin(kx) = (\exp(ikx) - \exp(-ikx)) / 2i \quad ((2))$$

Even though k represents a root mean square value, among the infinite values of p , one of them equals k , thus from the point of view of $W(x)$, the wavefunction, it is as if this single plane wave and its reflected term ($\exp(-ikx)$) with a phase of 3.14 comprise the wavefunction.

If one calculates momentum Shannon's entropy $-\sum p \ln(p)$, as the authors of (1) do, then the two approaches are very different. If one simply uses $C/2i$ and $-C/2i$ as the p weights from ((2)), it seems one obtains a different result. When working with the spatial time independent Schrodinger equation, however, it seems ((2)) is sufficient.

If one were to add a finite potential which vanishes at the walls, but not in the interior, it seems that a double resonance might result. From a mathematical point of view, one may use $C \sin(kn x - b)$ as a basis for this new problem as these functions are complete and vanish at the walls. Each $\sin(kn x - b)$ is made of $\exp(i kn x)$ and $\exp(-i kn x)$. Thus, there seem to be two schemes to describe the same overall wavefunction. First, the new wavefunction is given by:

$$W(x) = \sum_{p=6.28n/L} f_{p,n} \sin(ipn x) \quad \text{where } L \text{ is the length of the box} \quad ((3))$$

According to (1), p_n is the root mean square average momentum of state n , but it is also a specific p value associated with ((1)). Thus, one might argue that for each n , only $p = p_n$ dominates the problem, even though other p values are present.

In a previous note (2), it was argued one could write the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ expanded as Fourier series. In such a case:

$$p^2/2m \sum f_p + \sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j = E f_p \quad ((4))$$

For the box, p is restricted to $p=p_n=6.28n/L$, thus ((4)) is peculiar because V_k should scatter any p , not just special p_n 's. It seems that because there are two resonances in the system, one with $V(x)$ given by ((4)) and one with the wall, that only p_n values dominate the overall resonance. Apparently, other p values are present, but with low weights. If one decided not to use the basis $\sin(kn x - b)$, but to simply solve the Schrodinger equation with the restriction that $W(x)$ vanish at the walls, the same result would be obtained. There would again be special $p=p_n$ values only.

One may consider using the Fourier transform ((1)) of $\sin(kn x - b)$, which we denote by b_n, p . Here every value of p is allowed and b_n, p is of the form of ((1)). Then, an equation equivalent to ((4)) is:

$$p_n^2/2m \sum_j f_j b_{n,j} + \sum_{k+l=p_n} V_k f_l b_{n,l} = E_n \sum_j f_j b_{n,j} \quad ((5))$$

Where $p_n = 6.28n/L$.

Equating ((4)) and ((5)) allows for a solution of:

$$\sum_j f_j b_{n,j} = f p_n \quad ((6))$$

This seems to indicate that the momentum value p_n , for a specific n value, is the only important one for the state with root mean square momentum of f_n .

Thus, ((4)) seems to be similar to a kind of exclusion principle as all p 's except p_n 's are excluded (or have small weights). In such a case, V_k seems to only interact with these p_n 's in a dominant way (although it is really interacting with all p 's). Given that these p_n 's are associated with $6.28n/L$, the interactions with $V(x)$ are quantized in a sense. It seems, however, that the collisions with the walls (with an infinite potential) are ultimately responsible for this. The question we ask, however, is whether there is an oscillatory particle present mediating these p_n resonances?

The idea of a particle in a box with a finite potential everywhere except at the walls where the potential is infinite has been applied in the literature to compound nuclei. In such a case, the p_n resonances are important because they are used in the calculation of statistical mechanical quantities such as free energy. These, in turn, are used to calculate evaporation rates of nucleons from a hot nucleus.

Other Examples

For a harmonic oscillator, one may write solutions as $W_0(x) H_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. $W_0(x)$ is already a resonance which satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $E = \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega$ where $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$. Thus, $H_n(x)$ only enters the Schrodinger equation in the $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x)$ term and the pieces from this equation (other than $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W_0(x)$) are equal to $C H_n(x)$. Thus, a second resonance seems to be formed between $W_0(x)$ and $H_n(x)$ with energies of $\hbar \omega n$ where n is an integer. Thus, the problem again seems to be broken into two pieces. In this case, the $\hbar \omega n$ states from $H_n(x)$ can be thought of as related to phonons. It seems the oscillator equation is associated with physical phonon states for displaced atoms in a crystal etc. It seems one may generalize, as the wavefunction of other problems can be written as a product, with one factor being a resonance of the same Hamiltonian. For example, if $\sin(kn x)$ is a solution for a particle in a box with infinite walls, but no potential in the interior, then:

$$\sin(kn x) \cos(kn x) \quad ((7))$$

is also a solution, but with a different average energy. One may ask, however, whether there is anything physical about ((7)), in particular whether there is any reason to believe a physical $\sin(kn x)$ resonance is contained in the overall $\sin(kn x) \cos(kn x)$ resonance. On the other hand,

$\sin(kn x)$ is a resonance and $\cos(kn x)$ is a phase shifted result of the same resonance. It is possible there is some significance having the two together.

Mixed states are another case of a possible double resonance. Consider a Hamiltonian:

$$H = H_0 + bV(x) \text{ where } b \text{ is small and solutions of } H_0 \text{ are known. } \quad ((8))$$

From a mathematical point of view, if one knows solutions to H_0 i.e. W_0, W_1, W_2, \dots , these may be used as a basis for H . If one wants low energy, one may use $a W_0(x) + b W_1(x)$, for example to estimate the ground state of H . The question is whether this is only a math procedure, or whether $bV(x)$ is actually causing transitions from $W_0(x)$ to $W_1(x)$ with an oscillatory internal particle mediating the jump perhaps. Given that solutions of H_0 often have a certain symmetry, one can measure the solution of H and have it collapse into $W_0(x)$ or $W_1(x)$. This might lend credibility to the idea of the two resonances actually having physical meaning. An example is the deuteron wavefunction which is a sum of an $L=0$ and $L=2$ piece.

Finally, consider particles in a box with walls with an infinite potential and added photons. This leads to the traditional Fermi gas (or Bose-Einstein type gas) problem. In such a case, the photons are physical oscillatory mediators between the single particle states, but one is not forming a new wavefunction. One may ask why? It seems that in such a picture,:

$$\text{density}(x) = W_0(x)W_0(x) \exp(-E_0/T) + W_1(x) W_1(x) \exp(-E_1/T) + \text{etc}$$

The photons are not considered to act as a potential. It seems that for a potential $V(x)$, an interaction must occur exactly at point x , while a photon is absorbed over a long range of x and so leads from one specific resonance at time t_1 to another different resonance at time t_2 .

Consider:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) \quad ((9))$$

Here $v(x)$ is the classical velocity at x , which means that it too is defined at a point x . ((9)) seems to make use of complex conditional probabilities $P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. This probability sums to 1, but relies on the idea that an interaction occurs at a point x . This might explain why traditionally photons do not lead to a mixed state. If one, however, could have agitations at each point x related to some added energy, then one, it seems, could have a temperature dependent wavefunction obtained directly from a Schrodinger equation with a temperature dependent potential. This has been discussed in the literature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we wish to point out that a variety of quantum mechanical problems seem to make use of the idea of a double resonance. In particular, one first obtains quantized solutions of one problem, usually a simpler one, and then uses these, (perhaps as a basis, but not always) in the solution of a second quantum mechanical problem. Examples discussed include the particle in a box with infinite potential walls and a finite potential in the interior, the oscillator, mixed states and quantum statistical mechanics. We suggest this approach may be more than a mathematical convenience and that there may possibly be physical oscillatory particles associated with the first set of quantized states. These oscillatory particles might be associated with the second problem which involves jumps from one simpler states to another.

References

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